

DYNAMICS OF THE LEVELS OF RUSSIAN LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY OF STUDENTS OF NON-LINGUISTIC FACULTIES OF PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITIES IN UZBEKISTAN

Abzairov Takhir Yuldashevich

Teacher of the department of Russian language and literature

Termez State Pedagogical Institute

tel: +99890-246-92-70

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8059434>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 12th June 2023

Accepted: 19th June 2023

Online: 20th June 2023

KEY WORDS

Effectiveness, cultural, interdisciplinary, speech culture, detail, homogeneity, for successful communication, cognitive, control stages of the experiment.

ABSTRACT

An analysis of the results of experimental work to test the effectiveness and efficiency of the developed structural and functional model for the development of the linguistic personality of students in non-linguistic faculties of pedagogical universities in Uzbekistan based on an interdisciplinary approach is presented. The purpose, tasks and methods of research on the development of the linguistic personality of students on the basis of an interdisciplinary approach are described. The pedagogical experiment was carried out in three stages: ascertaining, forming, control. It was attended by 93 first-year students of the Termez State Pedagogical Institute.

In every society there are requirements for the upbringing and education of a person. Education is the process of creating a moral and spiritual foundation, and education is the process of developing the mental abilities of a child. The matter concerns two different aspects of human mental activity. There is no reason to think that education (development of mental abilities) gives the child moral development. You can meet very educated people, but completely ill-mannered and unspiritual, and, on the other hand, a completely uneducated peasant or a simple worker, but highly educated spiritually and morally.

Education is connected with upbringing - even the law on education reflects that "education is a single purposeful process of upbringing and training ...". Education consists of education and training. The result of learning (according to the teachings of John Dewey) are the skills of thinking - primarily the ability to self-learning. The development of such skills is a specific task of mental education. So, upbringing and education are not the same thing. The difference between upbringing and education is very accurately shown in Dahl's dictionary: upbringing is "care for the material and moral needs of a minor up to his age. In the highest sense - to teach, instruct, teach everything that is necessary for life. An educated person is one who has grown up in the usual rules of secular decency.

Inclusive students are currently mainly philologists and translators, as well as those who study Russian along with his other future specialty (most often the humanities) and plans to use Russian in his work, mainly firms. As a rule, for these students in international business, Russian is not the first, but the second or third foreign language, and their interest in the

cultures of the languages being studied is quite high. An important role in the organization of this work is played by the creation of a "success situation" by the teacher in the lesson. It helps a strong student to realize his potential in more labor-intensive and complex activities, and a weak student to perform a feasible amount of work. Successful, in my opinion, is the emotional mood created by a parable or fable, proverb or saying told by the teacher at the beginning of the lesson. Collaborative learning is also important. The main objective of this training is to learn together. The effectiveness of the development of the communicative competence of students studying Russian as a second language is closely related to the continuous monitoring of the educational process in order to identify its compliance with the qualities provided for by the state standard. The need for such analytical observation in the educational environment is beyond doubt. The purpose of this study is a comprehensive review of the phenomenon of pedagogical monitoring (PM) and its inclusion in the system of teaching Russian as a non-native language in modern conditions. Theoretical and empirical research methods were chosen as the main ones: conversation, survey, interview, modeling, etc. In the practice of teaching Russian as a non-native language, emphasis is placed on the diagnostic, activity and prognostic components of the learning process, the tasks of choosing optimal educational technologies are determined and implemented. To do this, it is necessary to systematically collect information about the educational achievements of the individual, fix the level of his training, adjust the process of obtaining knowledge and developing skills. Accordingly, we can talk about informational, evaluative, corrective functions of pedagogical monitoring. Scattered information obtained, for example, on the basis of sociological and psychological observations, in the PM unites socio-economic, psycho-physiological, cultural and aesthetic factors that influence the student into a system. This shows the adaptive function of the. PM provides a high level of objectivity and comparability of assessments of the quality of education at different levels, a combination of forms of traditional control, observation and testing in optimal proportions, the implementation of an individual approach to the student's learning activities based on versatile information about him, the algorithmization of the system for determining the level of communicative competence of Russian language learners. In addition, PM makes it possible to analyze the learning process in detail, determine the quality of didactic material, timely correct and coordinate the activities of the student and teacher, identify the effectiveness of the development of communicative competence at different stages of language learning, as well as predict and model the subsequent development of the motivational, intellectual and emotional spheres of the individual student.

PM, according to V.I. Andreev, there is a "system diagnostics of qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the effectiveness of the functioning and tendencies of self-development of the educational system" [1: 452-453]. "The objects of monitoring are the educational process and its results, the personal characteristics of all participants in the educational process, their needs and attitude towards the educational institution" [4: 264]. In our opinion, PM is aimed primarily at identifying the degree of compliance of the educational process with the expected learning outcome. The ideal objects for monitoring the level of development of the communicative culture of students studying Russian as a non-native language are communication skills, which are reflected in the educational standard, the

essence of which is a diagnostic description of the mandatory requirements (“minimum”) for the content and goals of teaching Russian as a non-native language at one level or another possession. This kind of standard is a normative description of learning objectives and can ensure the comparability of the results achieved by students at a particular level with a given sample.

The features of the PM, the results of which make it possible to increase its significance in structuring the educational process and enable the teacher to make the right tactical decisions, are duration, systematicity and regularity. It focuses on identifying the learning status of each individual student and observing the dynamics of his learning throughout the course.

The period of study at a university plays a decisive role in the development of the linguistic personality of students, since during this period the foundations of professional discourse are laid. At all stages of formation and development in the chosen specialization, the speech development of students is manifested in the improvement of the language and the mastery of professionally priority forms of communication. The problem of the development of a linguistic personality in the process of professional training is a complex and multifaceted task, requiring the search for new approaches that have a complex fundamental-philological and psychological-pedagogical basis of scientific ideas. We assume that in order to develop a linguistic personality, it is necessary to use the possibilities of an interdisciplinary approach in the process of professional training. The purpose of the article is to analyze the results of experimental work to test the effectiveness and efficiency of the structural and functional model of the development of the linguistic personality of students based on an interdisciplinary approach. To achieve the goal, the following tasks are indicated: to determine the essential characteristic of the linguistic personality of a student-philologist; identify the possibilities of an interdisciplinary approach in the development of a linguistic personality; to introduce into the educational process a structural and functional model of the development of a linguistic personality and the pedagogical conditions for its implementation; evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of the developed structural-functional model and carry out statistical data processing. The holistic process of the development of the linguistic personality of students requires the design of an appropriate model. After analyzing the models of formation and development of the linguistic personality of students of various specialties proposed by the authors (I. F. Borisova, A. A. Vorozhbitova, S. Yu. Godunova, N. A. Deryabina, I. F. Ptitsyna, N. G. Kantysheva, I. L. Savvina, I. V. Solovieva, etc.), we came to the conclusion that the existing scientific works did not consider the issue of designing a structural and functional model for the development of the linguistic personality of students on the basis of an interdisciplinary approach, which is the scientific novelty of this become.

An analysis of the scientific and pedagogical literature shows that a sufficient amount of achievements has been accumulated, devoted to certain aspects of this problem. This is evidenced by the works of N. A. Deryabina, N. D. Golev, N. A. Ippolitova, V. V. Krasnykh, T. N. Kochetkova, K. F. Sedov, S. G. Vorkachev, V. A. Maslova, A. N. Baranova, L. A. Shestak and others. A number of works examine in detail the formation, formation and development of a linguistic personality in relation to a preschooler (S.Kh. Dzhumanazarov), a schoolchild (E. N. Volodina, M. L. Malchevskaya, N. B. Muratova and others), students (Shoimkulova Kumush

Abdimazhitovna, Shomurodova Zuhra Bozor kizi, Tulisova Oybarchin Sanjar kizi, Vahobova Makhvash Khaidar kizi, Kholmuminova Munira Khusan kizi, Kholmurodova Sobira Sherali kizi, Yuldasheva Makhigul Anvar kizi, Yorieva Kimyohon Khudoykul kizi). The analysis of the works made it possible to notice that the studies mainly touch upon the development of the ability to master the Russian language, readiness for self-expression in speech in accordance with generally accepted norms, reflection and self-esteem for successful communication. Given the problem of this study, there is a need to clarify the structural and content characteristics of the phenomenon of "linguistic personality". Of course, the priority in developing the structure of a linguistic personality belongs to linguistics. So, in the structural aspect, verbal-semantic, cognitive, pragmatic components are distinguished. In the aspect of psycholinguistics, the intellectual, language and speech components are distinguished. In the pedagogical aspect, the structure of a linguistic personality is viewed through a hierarchy of competencies: linguistic, cognitive, pragmatic. From the standpoint of sociology, the structure of a linguistic personality includes three components: motivational, cognitive and functional. The analysis of scientific research made it possible to identify the main components of the linguistic personality of students in non-linguistic faculties of a pedagogical university, which are the criteria for its formation: cognitive (possession of communicative codes, the ability to evaluate and reflect on communicative situations); motivational-value (understanding the importance of speech activity in professional training and the development of motivation in improving communication and speech skills); emotional (understanding of emotional phenomena, characterized by the presence of reflection and adequate self-esteem); behavioral (the formation of a conscious perception of one's own and someone else's position in speech activity and the manifestation of cooperation and compromise in relation to the interlocutor). The purposeful use of an interdisciplinary approach in the professional training of students of non-linguistic faculties of a pedagogical university will ensure the development of a linguistic personality in a complex manner, influencing communicative, moral, aesthetic and cultural qualities and abilities, which will allow, along with professional competencies, to form competencies related to other areas of activity. Within the framework of this study, an interdisciplinary approach in the development of the linguistic personality of students in non-linguistic faculties of a pedagogical university, in the presence of certain pedagogical conditions, is defined as a set of goals, content, methods and forms of influence and interaction, educational and methodological support and measures in the educational process aimed at developing students non-linguistic faculties of a pedagogical university, components of a linguistic personality. A structural and functional model for the development of the linguistic personality of students in non-linguistic faculties of a pedagogical university was developed and introduced into the educational process of the Termez State Pedagogical Institute on the basis of an interdisciplinary approach, and a number of pedagogical conditions were identified that, in our opinion, implement it.

In the previous work, four interrelated blocks of the structural-functional model were characterized in more detail: target, theoretical-methodological, procedural-content and evaluative-effective. In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the developed structural-functional model, experimental work was carried out, which was carried out from 2021 to 2023 in three stages: ascertaining, forming and control. At the ascertaining stage of the

experiment, the following tasks were considered: analysis of the state of the problem of the development of the linguistic personality of students in non-linguistic faculties of a pedagogical university; substantiation of the structural and functional model of the development of a linguistic personality; compiling diagnostic tools and assessing the actual level of formation of the components of a linguistic personality among students of non-linguistic faculties of a pedagogical university. The first-year students of the Termez State Pedagogical Institute took part in the diagnosis of the actual level of formation of the components of the linguistic personality: the control group (CG) - 46 students; experimental group (EG) - 47 students.

A diagnostic toolkit was selected, which made it possible to study each criterion separately: cognitive - the author's questionnaire for assessing knowledge about the basics of speech culture, the author's test to identify communication skills, the ability to present information and evaluate the interlocutor; motivational-value - the author's test questionnaire on the representation of the essence of the profession, the author's questionnaire for assessing the motivational attitude to speech self-development, the questionnaire for assessing the motivation for success and the fear of failure (A. A. Rean); emotional - a method for diagnosing the level of development of reflexivity (A. V. Karpov), a method for studying qualitative emotional characteristics (L. A. Rabinovich), a method for diagnosing empathy (I. M. Yusupova); behavioral - an emotional intelligence questionnaire (D. V. Lyusin), a test of communication skills (L. Mikhelson), a test for assessing the level of sociability (V. F. Ryakhovsky), a test for assessing self-control in communication (M. Snyder).

Table 1 presents the results of the ascertaining stage of the experiment, which do not show a significant difference in the level of formation of the linguistic personality components in the EG and CG. The statistical calculation of the Mann-Whitney U-test was used for the reliability of this assumption, which allows comparing independent samples and checking their homogeneity for the significance of differences in the selected criteria of linguistic personality.

Table 1

The results of the formation of the components of the linguistic personality of students in the experimental and control groups (%)

The ascertaining stage of the experiment								
Levels	Cognitive (C)		Motivational-value (Mv)		Emotional (E)		Behavioral (B)	
	EG	CG	EG	CG	EG	CG	EG	CG
High	14	11	5	3	6	5	8	8
Medium	61	64	66	72	68	69	66	71
Low	28	28	35	31	31	29	32	25

Thus, the studied groups are homogeneous and suitable for the formative stage of the experiment. In order to test the effectiveness of the developed model and methodology for the development of a linguistic personality, a formative stage of the experiment was carried out, during which the structural-functional model was tested, the dynamics of the levels and indicators of the formation of all components was traced. In table. 2 shows the results of the formation of the linguistic personality of students in the EG and CG at the control stage of the

experiment. The results show that there is a significant increase in levels in all groups. However, in the experimental group, the level is much higher, therefore, the dynamics of the development of the four components is most pronounced.

Table 2

The results of the formation of the components of the linguistic personality of students in the experimental and control groups (%)

The ascertaining stage of the experiment								
Levels	Cognitive (C)		Motivational-value (Mv)		Emotional (E)		Behavioral (B)	
	EG	CG	EG	CG	EG	CG	EG	CG
High	34	16	27	9	43	22	36	12
Medium	66	74	71	77	55	67	63	80
Low	3	13	4	17	5	15	4	12

Thus, the study at the control stage of the experiment showed that the dynamics of the levels of formation of the components of the linguistic personality of students from the EG prevails in relation to the dynamics of the level indicators of students from the CG (Fig. 2). Summarizing the above, we note that in the course of experimental work, the developed structural and functional model of the development of the linguistic personality of students was tested (verified) and practically implemented on the basis of an interdisciplinary approach in the educational environment of the university. In the course of the experiment, the efficiency and effectiveness of the model was evaluated, its necessary correction was carried out, the experimental material was generalized, and a comparative and statistical analysis of diagnostics in the EG and CG was carried out. In conclusion, it should be noted that the success of a comparative analysis of the results of experimental data obtained during the ascertaining and control stages of the experiment showed that the most significant changes in the creation of certain conditions occurred in the experimental group, which indicates a high level of formation of the components of the students' linguistic personality. This confirms the effectiveness and efficiency of the developed structural-functional model for the development of the linguistic personality of students based on an interdisciplinary approach.

References:

1. Comenius Ya.A. Great didactics / Ya.A. Comenius. -M.: Pedagogy, 1989. - 416 p.
2. Russian as a foreign language (pre-university stage of education, level B1+): textbook. allowance / D.N. Ilyin [i dr.]. Rostov n/a; Taganrog: Publishing House of Southern Federal University, 2018. 152 p.
3. Preparation for the final exam in Russian as a foreign language at the stage of pre-university education / D.N. Ilyin [i dr.]. // Russian test: theory and practice. 2018. No. 6. S. 18-23.
4. Arefiev A.L. Russian language in the world: past, present, future // Bulletin of the Russian Academy of Sciences. 2014. V. 84, No. 10. S. 896-903.
5. Tursunova S.I. (2022). Person and education is a society question. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 2(5), 381 - 387. Retrieved from <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/2973>

6. Shevchenko M. S. Diagnostic tools for assessing the results of the formation of the components of the linguistic personality of students-philologists // Questions of Pedagogy. 2021. No. 4-1. URL: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=45616856>
7. Gaskon Elena Alexandrovna - Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor of FSBEI HE "Tver State University", (170100, Tver, Zhelyabova St., 33), e-mail: pchel_ea@mail.ru
8. Actual problems of studying and teaching Russian as a foreign language at a university in the context of the internationalization of education: Mat. II Intern. seminar dedicated to the 15th anniversary of academic cooperation between Tver State University and Finnish universities. Tver: Tver. state un-t, 2015. S. 48-59.